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EMOTIONAL DESIGN CAN IMPROVE THE HEALTH

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ABSTRACT

The statistics shows that consuming milk in Iran is less than the average in the world. Since consuming milk has an important role in children health, it is necessary to persuade them to drink it. In this study emotional packaging was investigated to find the role of emotional design in children decisions on drinking milk. For this aim Kansei Engineering was used. 10 milk packages were selected among 100 samples. A representative package was chosen for each category. 10 packages were selected to be studied. According to the choice of domain in Kansei Engineering, the representatives have been evaluated by Kansei words with 50 students, between 7-11 years old.

It is concluded that using emotional design encouraging users to drink milk. It proves the key role of design in human life. Emotional design can help people to improve their health by provoking them to consume healthy products such as milk.

Keywords: Emotional Design, Kansei Engineering, Milk Packaging

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays emotional design has an important role in product purchasing. Emotional design has recognized as a fundamental branch of design in the latter part of the 20th century Chapman (2005). Considering organization's objectives and customers wants will increase design value Best (2006). Customer needs can be considered based on how easy the user can express them and the speed of changing needs Otto & Wood (2001). Today people become more sensitive to different aspects of products; designers should understand emotional needs and create an appropriate connection between people and

products. Nowadays design requires a special awareness and corresponding position in market Zec (2007). Designers can use natural properties of human and also the world in their design. They should study natural relationship and concentrate in design to provide users' needs better Norman (1990).

Of course, emotion has always played an elementary role in all forms of design and creation, both from the designer and user perspective Chapman (2005). More over emotions have a significant role in daily lives. Emotional expressions let us know peoples motivations and desires, accomplishments and frustration Norman (2004).

Emotional design can play an effective role in packaging. Consumers are linked with the quality of the product by packaging. Packaging also protects the safe and gentle qualities of product Kozak & Wiedemann (2008). Since attractive things seem to be easier to use Norman (2004) attractive packages can encourage consumer to use the product.

In today competitive world of packaging designers have to work harder in food products (Wells et al, 2007). Package uses its power to notice the product among the compression of competitive world.

Nowadays the importance of packaging as a communication tool is growing (Silayoi & speece, 2007).

Packaging protects the product against some damages such as: climate condition, transportation and biological hazards (Wells et al, 2007). Packaging may seem to be more than a protective container, but as the external manifestation of a product, its role is much more pivotal. Packaging design needs to reflect the emotional relationship to connect the consumer to the product.

Packaging as a main type of protection is still required; however packaging should also be considered in the promotional strategy (El-omari,

1998). Designers can create new packaging to identify the brand. They can also give packaging varieties to be more than a functional container King Gordon (2005).

From the consumer point of view, packaging plays a key role when products are purchased. The package becomes a critical factor in the consumer decision-making procedure. It should be mentioned that consumers are highly motivated by their positive or negative emotions (Wells et al, 2007). Package designers must consider consumers past experiences, needs and wants. They should realize how package design features, get consumers attention (Silayoi & Speece, 2007).

Consuming milk has an important role in children health. The statistics shows that consuming milk in Iran is less than the average in the world. Since, the importance of drinking milk for children, it is essential to persuade them to drink it. In this study emotional packaging was investigated to find out the effect of emotional packaging in consumption of milk on children. For this purpose Kansei Engineering method was used which is one of the first and foremost in product development methodology. Kansei Engineering is one of the practical methodologies which translates users' impressions, feelings and wants to product properties and concrete design parameters (Schütte & Eklund, 2001). In this paper Kansei Engineering methodology was used to link users emotions to product properties.

METHODOLOGY

“Kansei contains in its basic structure 4 important steps:

1. The collection of appropriate Kansei words due to the domain of the product.
2. Identifying the connection between the Kansei words and the design characteristics.
3. The building of the technological identification of the design characteristics.
4. Constructing a system connecting (1) to (3).” (Schütte & Eklund, 2001).

In this study, the first procedure was choice of domain.

CHOICE OF DOMAIN

In the choice of domain products samples which represent the domain are collected. The domain is defined by target group and user type, market segmentation and product specification (Schütte, 2005). So the domain was chosen. Firstly 250 samples were gathered. By the similarity and design characteristics forms, 100 samples were chosen. 10 representatives were selected by clustering. A representative package was chosen for each category. The representative package covered the most number of properties in each category; therefore 10 milk packages were selected to be studied. According to the choice of domain in Kansei Engineering, the representatives have been evaluated by Kansei words.

SPANNING THE SEMANTIC SPACE

The next procedure was spanning the semantic space.

In this methodology in higher levels Kansei is connected to the properties of products in the synthesis phase to gain a better result. Spanning the semantic space helps to have these levels of Kansei from a greater number of semantic expressions (Schütte, 2005). Three steps were done in this procedure which is explained below:

Collecting Kansei Words

Kansei words describe the choice of domain. Many sources should be used to have a complete selection of words. In this study 102 words were gathered from different sources such as experts, target group, literature, magazines and internet.

Kansei Structure Identification

By the expert group due to the choice of domain and target group specifications, Kansei Words were summarized. Clustering was used to summarize the words. Firstly 8 groups of words were identified then each Kansei word was cluster to its group. Then synonym words were omitted. For each group one representative was selected, therefore 16 words were selected as representatives for Kansei words. The selected Kansei words were: delicious, sweet, tasteless, tonic, fresh, dumb, luxury, exciting, funny, kind, extraordinary, addle, special, happy, sad, I love it.

SPANNING THE SPACE OF PROPERTIES

The third procedure was spanning the space of properties.

In this procedure due to the choice of domain potential properties were recognized. Then these properties were organized. Finally 20 physical properties were identified for milk packages. The defined properties were: plastic material, aluminum material, carton material, geometric, non-geometric, curved, broken lines, square shape, horizontal shape, formless, detailed, simple, complex, colorful, black and white, comic, familiar pictures, abstract pictures, warm colors and cold colors.

The next and important procedure was synthesis. In this procedure Kansei words and physical properties should be connected to each other. For this aim a case study was done.

CASE STUDY

50 students, between 7-11 years old were selected randomly. 25 were girls and 25 were boys. 10 milk packages were evaluated by Kansei words (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Representative Packages

This study was performed to understand the role of emotional packaging design in encouraging children to drink milk. The study was done by questionnaire and interview. The users’ expressions were closely observed. Questionnaires were given to participants and they were asked to explain their emotions regarding the attractiveness of the milk package through its color and style by means of the selected Kansei words. The facial and body reaction of the

users were also observed. The data were analyzed. By analyzing gathered data, the connection between semantic space and physical properties were recognized. The data also uncovered users' emotional wants. The results are presented in (Tables 1, 2, 3 and 4).

RESULTS

The results of the analysis of the data from questionnaire and interview are summarized below.

Kansei Words Milk Packages	Kansei Words							
	Sweet	Tonic	Exciting	Fresh	Kind	Funny	..	Sad
1	0	16%	24%	4%	4%	28%		16%
...								
3	0	0	24%	0	0	20%		68%
...								
5	12%	4%	28%	40%	56%	8%		4%
6	40%	0	8%	8%	4%	0		0
...								
10	20%	48%	0	4%	4%	0		0

Table 1. Importance of Kansei words in samples by girls

Kansei Words Milk Packages	Kansei Words							
	Sweet	Tonic	Exciting	Fresh	Kind	Funny	..	Sad
1	0	8%	4%	4%		48%		8%
...								
3	0	4%	40%	0	8%	16%		64%
...								
5	16%	0	0	64%	56%	0		20%
6	64%	4%	4%	0	0	0		0
...								
10	16%	64%	4%	4%	4%	4%		4%

Table 2. Importance of Kansei words in samples by boys

Kansei Words Milk Packages	Kansei Words							
	Sweet	Tonic	Exciting	Fresh	Kind	Funny	..	Sad
1	0	12%	14%	4%	2%	38%		12%
...								
3	0	4%	20%	0	4%	18%		66%
...								
5	14%	0	14%	52%	56%	4%		12%
6	52%	6%	6%	4%	2%	0		0
...								
10	18%	56%	2%	4%	14%	2%		0

Table 3. Importance of Kansei words in samples by girls & boys

Package No. Properties	Package No.							
	1	...	3	...	5	6	...	10
Plastic material	0		0		0	1		0
Aluminum Material	0		0		0	0		0
Carton material	1		1		1	0		1
Geometric	0		0		0	0		1
Non geometric	1		1		1	1		0
Curved	1		0		1	1		0
Broken lines	0		1		0	0		0
Square shape	0		0		1	0		1
...								
Complex	1		1		1	0		0
Colorful	1		0		1	1		1
Comic	1		0		1	0		1
Black & white	0		1		0	0		0
Familiar pictures	1		1		1	1		1

Table 4. Relationship between physical properties and representative packages

Kansei Words Milk Package	Kansei Words							
	Sweet	Tonic	Exciting	Fresh	Kind	Funny	..	Sad
Plastic Material	1	0	0	0	0	0		0
Aluminum Material	0	0	0	0	0	0		0
Carton Material	0	1	1	1	1	1		1
Geometric	0	1	0	0	0	0		0
Non Geometric	1	0	1	1	1	1		1
Curved	1	0	0	1	1	1		0
Broken Lines	0	0	1	0	0	0		1
Square Shape	0	1	0	1	1	0		0
....								
Complex	1	0	1	1	1	1		1
Colorful	1	1	0	1	1	1		0
Comic	1	1	0	1	1	1		0
Black & White	0	0	1	0	0	0		1
Familiar Pictures	1	1	1	1	1	1		1

Table 5. Relationship between Kansei words and physical properties

DISCUSSION

By analyzed data, the connection between physical properties and Kansei words were recognized. As it was shown in table 3, package number 1 got the most score (38%) in Kansei word "funny". The physical properties which related to this Kansei words were: carton material, non-geometric form, curved lines, horizontal shape, comic, colorful. Package number 3 got the most score in Kansei word "sad" (66%) the recognized properties for this package were: non-geometric, broken lines, complex, black and white, with familiar picture. This package was in Batman style. That's why most of the boys love this package although the package is "sad". The main color of this package is black which had an impressive role in scoring to be sad. It shows the importance of favorite characters on children decisions. Package number 5

got the most score (56%) in Kansei word "kind". This Kansei word was connected to: non-geometric shape, curved lines, have detailed, comic, colorful with familiar picture. Most of the girls loved package number 5. It showed the importance of the sense of being kind and mild styles on girls' decisions. Package number 5 also got the most score in Kansei word "fresh". This package was luxury from girls' point of view although boys chose package number 8 in Kansei word "luxury". Package number 8 also was the most tasteless one from girls' point of view. Package number 8 was connected to physical properties such as: geometric form, square shape, formless, simple, black and white. Package number 6 got the most score (52%) in Kansei word "sweet". This Kansei word was connected to physical properties such as: plastic materials, non-geometric material, curved lines, formless, simple, and colorful, with familiar picture. The big strawberry as a familiar picture which is dropped in the milk elicits the emotion of being sweet. Package number 10 got the most score (56%) in Kansei word "tonic" which is related to these properties: geometric form, square shape, formless, simple, colorful, comic, with familiar picture.

CONCLUSION

The analyzed data showed the distinct different point of view in boy and girls in choosing packages. Most of the boys were interested in Batman style with broken lines, complex and non-geometric form although most of the girls were interested in mild and kind style. It should be mentioned that the most favorite package from boys' point of view was dumb from girls' point of view. It shows the importance of understanding users' emotional needs because it has a direct impression on users' decisions. It was concluded that identified physical properties have a strong impression on children decision on choosing milk packages. Using familiar pictures such as fresh fruits, popular comic and cartoon characters, non-geometric shape, curved lines, using details with colorful packages encourage children to choose a package of milk. It proves the significant role of design and considering users' emotions. This study showed that by considering children emotional needs designers can provoke them to drink milk and help them to be healthier. Instead of many

advertisements and giving children advise about drinking milk and make them bored, we can offer them healthy food in lovely style. The key factor is to study and understand their lovely style. In this paper, children lovely style for milk package was investigated. By this research their emotional wants linked to physical properties for milk packages. Using these physical properties would encourage them to drink more milk and increase the amount of consumption of milk. By this means designers can improve the health in children.

REFERENCES

- El-Omari, H.A. (1998) The promotional role of packaging in attracting Jordanian consumers' attention to local products, *J. King Saud Univ*, Vol. 10, 107-118.
- Schutte, S., Eklund, J., (2001) An approach to Kansei Engineering Methods and a Case Study on Design Identity. Asean Academic Press, London.
- Silayoi, P. Speece, Mark., (2007) The importance of packaging attributes: a conjoint analysis approach. *European Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 41, No. 2, 1495-1517.
- Wells, L.E., Farley, H. & Armstrong, G.A., (2007) The importance of packaging design for own-label food brands. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 35, No. 9, 677-690.
- Best, K. (2006) Design management. Switzerland: Ava.
- Chapman, J. (2005) Emotionally durable design. UK: Earth Scan.
- King Gordon, s. (2005) Packaging make overs. USA: Rockport.
- Kozak, G., Wiedemann, J. (2008) Package design now. Germany: Taschen.
- Norman, D.A. (1988) The design of everyday things. New York: Basic Books.
- Norman, D.A (2004) Emotional design: Why we love or hate everyday things. New York: Basic Books.
- Otto ,K., Wood, K. (2001) Product design: Techniques in reverse engineering and new product development. India: Pearson Education.
- Edited by Zec, P. (2007) Hall of fame: Design for a better quality of life. Montreal: ICSID.
- Schütte, S. (2005) Engineering emotional values in product design, PhD, Thesis, Linköping University, Sweden.